

D4.1

Project website and graphical identity material

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1. Executive Summary

The INTERSECT website has been developed by the CNR coordinator team with input by fellow partners. The project website is a key element of the project dissemination strategy. It will be used to raise awareness and spread information inside the project consortium and beyond for the purposes of community building.

The website is a live communication tool: now it provides an introductory suite of pages that give an overview of the INTERSECT project, and it will develop and enrich as the project progresses to provide details of the project activities, outcomes and results.

2. Introduction

The INTERSECT website is part of the WP4 “Exploitation, dissemination & communication”, and precisely the Task 4.3 “Communication activities”.

The strategic goal of the whole communication strategy is to support the objectives for dissemination, exploitation and sustainability through regular stakeholder outreach and tailored messages. The strategy is to channel the results of the project towards different media, which are better suited for the communication towards end-users, citizens, civil organizations, and policy makers.

The engagement with stakeholders includes several tools as:

- press release to make the different stakeholders aware of the project start and to diffuse information in mass media
- a strong project identity (logo, web site) to increase the visibility of the project in search engines
- public, European events organized such as EC concertation or EMMC meetings
- local events organized through national scientific or funding agencies, as well as using local media such as local radio stations or newspapers
- panel or round table organized as satellite of workshops or conferences
- demonstration of the project results towards customers: major improvements and results of INTERSECT project will be reported in *ad hoc* newsletter
- social media: news will be distributed by social media channels such as Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn
- a ResearchGate group for the project
- a didactic video will be produced to explain in very simple terms the objectives of INTERSECT, and its societal benefits and YouTube pills will demonstrate the main features and capabilities of **IM2D** tool box
- general public outreach actions;

- open days: most of the partners are organizing open days where the public at large can visit the facilities and interact with scientists. Researchers involved in the project will be around to explain about the IM2D possible advantages and interact with visitors
- research website on EUROPA – the EU’s web portal allows massive connection across EU and outside.

In this deliverable we focus our attention on the project website and the graphical identity.

3. Visual Identity

For the INTERSECT project we were looking for a clear project identity, so we decided to realize a logo and visual identity guidelines, in order to convey its core messages to the public. These were then graphically developed by a professional communication agency (Mediamo, Modena IT) that produced a brand identity manual (February 2019).

The INTERSECT visual identity style is simple, direct, clear and geometrical.

The main features of these visual identity guidelines are:

- Colours: teal (Pantone 3541C, #00929e) and yellow ochre (Pantone 144C, #EA961C).
- Font: Poppins, google font.
- Logo: geometric and essential, it is composed by the project name with a stylized rendering of a synaptic circuit on the first two letters to convey the idea of neural interconnections and semantic interoperability. These elements show the INTERSECT ambition to pursue and accelerate the innovation process for the design of defective complex materials and devices for application in disruptive electronics and sensor industries.

Figure 1: INTERSECT logo

The consortium is bound to follow the brand identity guidelines, in order to boost the sense of belonging to the INTERSECT community and to make its visual identity gradually familiar to the external audience.

4. Website

According to the above-mentioned communication strategy, the website of the INTERSECT project is intended to be the main communication tool for

- providing all core information about the projects (who, what, why, how)
- internal and external communication about the project and the consortium activities

- scientific communication activities, aimed at (i) engaging the wider public in INTERSECT research results and (ii) informing about developments and progresses in materials and device modelling supporting European industries
- dissemination and outreach activities towards industrial stakeholders, associations, networks, general public and potential customers about the project's achievements.

The website can be reached at <http://intersect-project.eu/>.

It has been developed by a media agency and is continuously updated by the management staff at CNR.

Figure 2: INTERSECT homepage

The template is responsive and presents a scrolling home page, while internal pages and posts are traditional. The main colours are teal and ochre, in agreement with the project's brand identity. In the homepage are shown the main aspects of the INTERSECT project: the *abstract* of the project mission and goals, a *people* section, a *news and events* list, a *Consortium* description with a list of the partners and a colophon with contacts, social media links and acknowledgement of the Horizon 2020 European funding.

So far the website is organized into 5 sections that are linked in the menu bar (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: INTERSECT website sections

Other sections will be added if necessary.

Description of sections:

Abstract: is a short presentation of the project, describing the main goals of the project and explaining the partners involved (with links to the official webpage of each institution).

Open Positions: provides a showcase of the INTERSECT-funded job positions, giving all useful information about applications.

Open positions

PostDoc fellowship @CNR Nano
1 Postdoc fellowship. "Development of scientific computing software (also in MPI-environment) for the study of complex models and electronic devices for synaptic electronics and neuromorphic computing".

One position for research physics/computational materials scientist is available in the group of Dr. Arrigo Calzolari at CNR Nano in Modena, Italy, in the framework of EU-funded project "Interoperable Material-to-Device Simulation box for disruptive electronics - INTERSECT" - GA nr. 814487 (<http://intersect-project.eu/>). Outstanding candidates are sought with a background in the physical sciences alongside strong programming skills. Women are strongly encouraged to apply.

Candidates must have

- a master degree in Physics, Chemistry, Electronic Engineering or Computer Engineering.
- a PhD degree in Physics, Chemistry, Electronic Engineering or Computer Engineering.
- a 3-year or more experience in the study of solid-state systems and nanosciences based on the Functional Density Theory, or a PhD in relevant subjects.
- advanced knowledge of written and spoken English
- knowledge of programming language such as Fortran and/or MPI C; good knowledge of object-oriented programming (e.g. Python).

Within the INTERSECT project, this activity will aim at accelerating the uptake of materials modelling software in the field of synaptic electronics and neuromorphic computing to provide industry-ready software solutions. In particular, the candidate will be involved in the development/implementation of an interoperable, interdisciplinary and multi-physics simulation platform for simulation of disruptive electronics. This includes a software integration action, by means of the linking-and-coupling of existing materials and device simulation codes, as well as the formalization/development of specific workflows for the automation of the process that control the entire modelling pipeline.

Deadline: 03/03/2019
 For information on the positions, please contact intersect@nano.cnr.it.

Complete announcement available for download

Figure 4: example of news in the Open positions page

News: contains all the news and events related to the project. Each news is linked to a dedicated page with complete information and useful details.

09 April, 2019 - INTERSECT MEETING In Barcelona
 18 March, 2019 - Tutorial On Writing Reproducible Workflows For Computational Materials Science
 28 February, 2019 - INTERSECT SEMINAR - Prof. Marco Bernasconi
 09 January, 2019 - INTERSECT KICK-OFF MEETING

09 Jan INTERSECT KICK-OFF MEETING
 Posted at 15:55h in news by admin...intersect

Dear Partners,
 the INTERSECT kick-off meeting is planned for **Monday February 4 and Tuesday February 5, 2019 in Modena (IT)**.

Updated agenda: [download pdf](#)
 Monday 04/02 - Afternoon Session: from 14.00 to 19.30 + SOCIAL DINNER (from 20.00)
 Tuesday 05/02 - Morning Session - Public session: from 9.00 to 13.00 + FREE LUNCH + GOVERNING BOARD (from 13.00 to 15.00)

Registration here

Please register as soon as possible!

Venue: Accademia Nazionale di Scienza, Lettere ed Arti - Corso Vittorio Emanuele II, 59 [website](#) (5 minutes' walk from the railway station and from selected hotels).
Social Dinner: Ristorante Liva d'Oro, piazza Mazzini 38, Modena [website](#)

How to reach us:

By plane: The closest airport is Bologna Airport "Guglielmo Marconi" (40 Km). From there you can take the Aerbuss, a bus that runs directly to Modena every two hours. Tickets are available on board: one-way fare is € 15.00, round trip is € 25.00. To go to the city centre (where hotels and the Meeting venue are) stop at "Largo Garibaldi".
 A bus service connects the airport to the railway station Bologna Centrale, from Bologna Centrale, follow "by train" instructions).

Fig. 5 Examples of the news section: the news list and the detail regarding one specific event.

Contacts: this section shows, on the map, the location of the partners and the contacts to reach the project coordinator and management staff.

Intranet: is a private section accessible by the partners. It is a repository of the project documents and information. A complete description of intranet is available in the D5.1 at point 3.1.

In addition the central band of the scrolling web page presents a *People* section with a complete overview of the researchers involved in the project; it is linked to a dedicated page containing all the info about the project PI (with a short bio) and the teams involved.

According to needs, the new pages and sections can be added to the website.

5. Social Media

Three social media accounts have been opened in order to convey different messages to different audiences. It can be reached at:

Twitter: [@intersect_eu](#). News of interest from the project's life, from the research or scientific environment, and from the European research ecosystem have been tweeted or retweeted. The partners have been involved in this activity, as content creators or to help with the medium's boost effect by retweeting contents. A Twitter feed is available in the website homepage.

Linkedin: [intersect-project](#) (free company page). The page is open but still under development. We think it might be more useful when some results will be ready to be disseminated to industrial stakeholders, due to its specific feature of being a professional social media network.

Instagram: [intersect_eu](#). Same as above, the page is still at its beginning, we have shown images from Intersect life and expect to make an effort in showing soon some of the project's results.

Figure 6 examples of the social media pages of the INTERSECT project: Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn

6. Conclusions

The project identity and the website have been developed according to Task 4.3, now a greater effort has to be put in the communication activities. The project has been set up, most of the activities have geared up and it's high time we started conveying the results of our work in an effective communication strategy addressing public awareness and industrial/technological/scientific stakeholders.

A proper communication plan will be drafted in the next months and presented and discussed at the Intersect meeting to be held in Barcelona next September.